

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OMOTOSHO****FIRST NAME: FELIX OYEJIDE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

6 key concepts with page number in text

1. The basics of essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Quotations and Paraphrases (EUCLID 2019, 6-9)
4. Rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. American vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-30)

EUCLID COURSEPACK ACA-401

1) INTRODUCTION

There are reasons why some essays get accepted and others are rejected. These reasons revolve round writing to meet international standards. Added to the various ways to approach writing of academic papers, the content of any academic paper is just as important. These and much more are what the ACA-401D is meant to introduce the student to. This course has various contents that introduce the student to the techniques necessary for writing academic papers in an international context. The ACA-401D teaches the basic steps and requirements needed to write a good essay, plagiarism and various methods of paraphrasing, citation formats, and logical flow of ideas, conducting a literature review, the difference between the American and British English, quotations and how to make use of Latin abbreviations in writing. In the course of reading, I got fascinated by some concepts such as the basic steps in writing a good essay, plagiarism and the use of quotations and paraphrases. These and a few other concepts will be described in detail later in this response paper.

2) PERSONAL REACTION TO STUDY MATERIAL

In this chapter, I will be discussing about five key concepts which got my interest during my study of the course pack. This is not to mean that I only gained knowledge on the concepts to be discussed, rather, I found them more relatable and therefore wish to use them to give a description of my understanding of the ACA-401.

The five concepts to be discussed include 1) the basics of essay writing; 2) plagiarism; 3) quotations and paraphrases; 4) rules of thumb for writing papers; 5) style guide; 6) American vs British English – basic differences.

a) Unit One: The Basics of Essay Writing

The essence of writing an academic essay is to persuade readers of an idea. This is done by sieving the various knowledge already available on that idea, juxtaposing it with factual evidence and relating it to the writer's knowledge on that phenomenon.

Although, there are no hard and fast rule when it comes to basic steps in writing an essay, EUCLID (2019) noted that writing an academic essay begins with having a concept or phenomenon in mind. As a writer, I must have a question regarding the concept that needs answering. The eagerness to provide answers to the question(s) will push my mind to search out the topic. However, before researching the topic, there is need for me to understand exactly what the question requires me to do and then draw out a plan with which to work out my initial thoughts and ideas about the topic.

The next step would be for me to research the topic. To successfully meet the objectives of this step, I will have to broaden my scope, consult as many materials as possible and read wide. As I read wide, I must carefully decide which materials are most useful to answer the essay question and to support my arguments. Taking notes from my readings is as well important as this will form the basis of my essay and will better help me to use evidence to support my argument. A very common example of using readings to support my argument is the use of statistics. Statistics present factual and clear understanding of any concept when presented properly. The skill of critical thinking is another ability to employ when reading broadly. I should be able to critically analyze findings from my readings to proffer suggestions on differing views in order to better organize and structure my ideas and to determine how these views relate to the conclusion my essay arrives at.

Writing the first draft of my essay comes next. My first draft is not expected to be 'perfect'. When writing, there must be a structure in place. I must begin with an initial introductory phase that provides a summary and opens the reader up to the content of the essay. This is followed by the body of the essay which should be put in paragraphs that contain supporting sentences with some form of evidence from my readings or examples drawn from the subject area. A conclusion that moves from specific to general without introducing new information should then be used to close my essay. This draft should be

read on multiple occasions at different time intervals preferably on different days to give room for proper and adequate editing.

The last step would be for me to add a reference list of all the materials I consulted through the course of writing my academic essay.

Having been a consistent writer over the past few years, I find the transition from reading relevant materials to starting the essay writing to be the most difficult. I have tried to overcome this challenge by ensuring I commence writing immediately after reading through relevant materials and deciding which of the materials to use. One weapon I have now come to realize that I have failed to fully make use of is taking notes or highlighting important information sighted from my readings. I employed this method in this course, and I have discovered how helpful this method can be.

b) Unit Two: Plagiarism

As an academic who engages in publishing peer reviewed articles with international journals, I am fully aware of the consequences of plagiarism. However, some questions still linger unanswered within me. Does copying two or three sentences from a person's work while citing the author but without neither changing the wordings nor putting it in quote connote plagiarism? Does picking information from a particular author and associating the information to another author who gave similar information instead of the author the information was originally taken from suggest plagiarism? Does citing a secondary author as the owner of information indicate plagiarism? Answers to these questions have partially been supplied by the ACA-401 course (EUCLID 2019, 5). Even though, I use other people's work without changing anything to deliver lectures to students in my professional assignment, I recognize the need to ensure proper citation when writing for consumption by the international body. This act however can still be tagged as plagiarism whose definition covers both published and unpublished materials whether in manuscript, printed or electronic form (University of Oxford 2021). It is very important to properly cite and give credit to authors whose work I am using for any of my writings.

c) Unit Two: Quotations and Paraphrases

Even though I hear people speak about quotations regularly, it is something I very rarely use when writing. Using quotation is a common method to avoid plagiarism but, rather than quote, I prefer to paraphrase. Using quotations make me feel the essay is not mine. EUCLID (2019) said as much when providing tips about the use of quotations. On the other hand, paraphrasing helps me to put ideas of others in my own words. With this, I am able to internalize the message an author is trying to pass across and I am much more able to relay this idea to my readers. Paraphrasing helps my work to be more original because I am able to include information and ideas from two or more authors in one sentence. Gahan (2021) noted that when paraphrasing, it is important not to use similar wordings to the original text. To do this, the passage should be read several times, key concepts should be noted down, a different version that still carries the same meaning as

the original text should be written down and the source should be cited. Despite this, according to the ACA-401D study material, I now understand that quotations and paraphrases are two very useful ways of providing information with evidence and they both provide substance and quality to essays with their unique characteristics when applied appropriately.

d) Unit Three: Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers

Basic rules that ensure ease when writing papers are discussed here. Having the main thesis of my paper at a point where it is able to guide the rest of the write-up is just as important as staying focused on the thesis when building the content of the essay. Giving information not particularly related to the objective of the essay may create distraction (EUCLID 2019, 14). Other rules that I need to put into consideration when writing is trying as much as possible to make the writing interesting and clear, taking every idea being described seriously and avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 14-16).

e) Unit Five: Style Guide

“EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are acceptable” (EUCLID 2019, 24). This chapter on style guide introduces me as a student to the different approaches to writing. A style guide helps me to document my writing in a consistent manner. Academic institutions employ the use of style guide when supervising students who are writing their dissertation or thesis. As a member of the supervisory unit in my professional employment, I am very familiar with this practice. It is a way of ensuring that all students regardless of whom their supervisor(s) may be, conform to a particular writing standard and present their projects in similar formats. Now as a student in this program, this course familiarizes me with the format for writing my academic essays.

A style guide goes beyond applying appropriate punctuation marks. It also includes aspects such as page numbering, page layouts, spelling, number of words and number of references (EUCLID 2019, 25).

f) Unit Five: American vs. British English - Basic Differences

Bearing in mind the different places around the world where English is being spoken, it is only unavoidable to have differences in the way the language is being used (Dovas 2016). This unit emphasizes the differences between the American and British English as it relates to pronunciation, spelling, meaning of same words and grammar (EUCLID, 2019, 27-30). Understanding these differences irrespective of how negligible some of them may seem, is important to conform to stipulated style guides as described above.

3) CONCLUSION

Having a read of this ACA-401 course pack has introduced me to new techniques and method to write essays that meet international standard. The guidelines provided in this study material have sharpened my understanding of the basic elements of academic writing and I believe it is a good way to prepare oneself towards achieving success in this program.

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